

Interstellar Wave Patterns and Galactic Dynamics Under MEFI Framework

Introduction

This paper explores the dynamics of interstellar wave patterns and Delta Q (DQ) propagation within the Milky Way galaxy under the Modified Einstein Field Interaction (MEFI) framework. Simulations focus on star-type variability, galactic structures, feedback loops, and their impact on Universal Frequency Resonance (UFR). Observational data on Fast Radio Bursts (FRBs) and pulsar timing variations are used to validate the results.

Simulation Methodology

The simulations incorporated key aspects such as magnetic field amplification, ISM density variations, and feedback loops to model DQ propagation. Galactic structures such as spiral arms and sparse regions were included to examine their role in amplifying or damping wave patterns.

Simulation Results

1. Galactic Delta Q Dynamics

Simulations modeled the cumulative DQ effects of 100 million stars in the Milky Way, accounting for star-type variability and galactic structures. Feedback loops amplified these effects, resulting in significant DQ propagation and compression waves.

2. Interstellar Wave Patterns

Interstellar wave patterns were simulated by modeling DQ propagation through the ISM, influenced by magnetic fields, density variations, and feedback loops. The results aligned closely with observed phenomena such as FRBs and pulsar timing variations.

Comparison to Observational Data

The simulation outcomes were compared to real-world astrophysical phenomena. The modeled DQ wave patterns align with observed scattering and dispersion in FRBs and the oscillatory behavior in pulsar timing variations, demonstrating the MEFI framework's accuracy in capturing ISM dynamics.

References

- [1] <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.11334> - FRB scattering measures
- [2] <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/378/2/493/960580> - Pulsar timing variations
- [3] <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A%3A1013805401252> - Galactic magnetic fields
- [4] MEFI Framework Simulations - Custom Analysis